

The Role of Energy Storage in Germany

Daniel Rüdert
Thomas Gilon
Virio Andreyana
Martha Frysztacki

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Executive Summary

"The Role of Energy Storage in Germany" focuses on investigating multi-day storage solutions, specifically 100h Iron-Air batteries and their system benefits in Germany 2035.

Low-cost Multi-Day Storage (MDS) has great potential to **reduce curtailment, flatten electricity prices and reduce resource dependency** while helping to meet emissions targets.

Its benefits support delays in transmission projects and a mandated phase-out of gas power plants, especially during multi-day dark doldrums. It offers a particularly strong case in extreme weather year scenarios with optimized installed Iron-Air battery capacities of up to 31 GW in Germany.

The project [GitHub repository](#) includes a fully open and reproducible workflow and comprehensive [documentation](#).

Figure 1: Installed Iron-Air capacities in Germany 2035 for climate year 2010 with low Iron-Air investment cost

Motivation

- Alongside G7 nations, Germany aims to reach **near 100% clean power by 2035** [1].
- The role of **energy storage** within the German power system is not well discussed yet.
- Often, models do not show cost-optimal investments in **multi-day storages (MDS)** due to low temporal resolutions, emphasizing the need for highly granular optimization with **annual perfect foresight** modelling over **multiple climate years**.
- Therefore, the aim of this study was to develop a comprehensive understanding of the system impact of these long-duration **multi-day storage technologies for 2035**.
- Important **policies** such as the country's National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) are considered in our methodology.

Methodology

■ Study scope and baseline assumptions

- Sector-coupled model **PyPSA-Eur** for **2035**:
power, electric transport and heating sectors included
- Countries: AT, BE, CH, CZ, **DE**, DK, FR, IT, LU, NL, PL, SE
- Spatial resolution: **52 nodes**
(31 nodes for DE, 6 nodes for FR, 5 nodes for IT and 1-2 for other grid neighbours)
- Temporal resolution: **4380 segments (equivalent to avg. 2H)**
- “Netzentwicklungsplan” ([NEP](#)) electricity transmission grid projects included [2]
 - HVAC lines included (6% fixed expansion)
 - HVDC links optional (11% optional endogenous expansion)
- Inclusion of **Net Transfer Capacities (NTCs)** between neighboring countries from [ENTSO-E TYNDP 2022 IoSN](#) [3]
- **Emission limit** based on (interpolated) targets of included countries and limited to power and heating sectors based on [European Commission \(2024\)](#): **10.7% of 1990s emissions** [4]

Figure 2: Clustered electricity grid for the scope of the study

Methodology

■ Study scope and baseline assumptions

- **Vehicle to grid** included based on Germany's national energy and climate plan with electric vehicle share of **30%**, availability of **20%** and power rating of **7 kW** [5]
- **Phase out** of German conventional power plants (except gas)
- Gas price updated to **38 EUR/MWh** ([RePowerEU project](#)) [6]
- Nuclear generation of **at least 50% of the rated power** based on historical data from [Réseaux Énergies](#) profile and [EDF](#) profile [7,8]
- Increased **electricity demand** by **+26%** compared to PyPSA default electricity demand data (2013). Uses 2035 forecast based on German [Agora study](#) to account for increased industrial electrification which we are otherwise not modeling within our scope [9]
- Updated cost and lifetime assumptions for **Adiabatic Compressed Air Energy Storage (CAES)** based on publicly reported data [10-13]
 - Lifetime: 40 years
 - CAPEX: €1.700/kW power + €30/kWh energy (in 2022€)

Figure 2: Clustered electricity grid for the scope of the study

Methodology

■ Study scope and baseline assumptions

- **Heating sector assumptions** analogue to assumptions in PyPSA-DE of [Ariadne](#) project based on numbers of German BMWK [14]:
 - District Heating potential: 30%
 - Space heat reduction: 21%
- **Limits on CO2 sequestration** (22.3 MtCO₂) and **Direct Air Capture (DAC)** (12.4 MtCO₂) adapted to the scope of the study and based on the [European Commission Industrial Carbon Management \(COM/2024/62\)](#) [15]

Figure 2: Clustered electricity grid for the scope of the study

Methodology

■ Governing assumptions for the scenario storylines

- **Climate year 2013:** These scenarios use the default weather year for PyPSA-Eur chosen as representative weather year in the upper median of [Gøtske et al. \(2024\)](#) [16]. This is also the default climate year for our baseline scenario.
- **Climate year 1996:** These scenarios are based on the climate year 1996, which is characterised by low yield of PV and wind, as well as a pronounced “dark doldrums” for about 10 days in January [17].
- **Climate year 2010:** These scenarios are based on the climate year 2010, which is characterised by the lowest annual wind resources and the second highest annual heating demand from 1960 - 2021 [16].
- **Climate year 2012:** These scenarios are based on the climate year 2012, which is the most stressful climate year in terms of 2-week dark doldrum situation at European aggregated level [18].
- **Mandated German gas phase out:** These scenarios assume that Germany, driven by policy decision, successfully phases out gas-fired power plants and gas CHPs in the power sector in 2035.
- **Delayed transmission expansion:** These scenarios assume that Germany’s ‘NEP’ transmission projects face delays, with only confirmed HVAC lines and HVDC links available that are to be built before and including 2032 [2].
- **Gas price sensitivity:** These scenarios assume that the EU’s gas market faces a 50% price increase to 58 EUR/MWh compared to the baseline scenario.
- All scenarios are complemented with **counterfactual** runs where multi-day storages are excluded. They are referred to as **‘no MDS’ scenarios**.

Methodology

■ Set of **16 scenarios** starting from a moderate baseline scenario

Storyline \ Iron-Air cost	High Iron-Air cost (23.50 € ₂₀₂₄ /kWh)	Medium Iron-Air cost (20.00 € ₂₀₂₄ /kWh)	Low Iron-Air cost (15.25 € ₂₀₂₄ /kWh)
Climate year 2013	baseline	mid-capex	low-capex
Climate year 2012	cy2012	cy2012-mid-capex	cy2012-low-capex
Climate year 1996	cy1996	-	-
Climate year 2010	cy2010	cy2010-mid-capex	cy2010-low-capex
Mandated German gas phase out	-	nogasppde-mid-capex	nogasppde-low-capex
Delayed transmission expansion	-	delayed-nep-mid-capex	delayed-nep-low-capex
Gas price sensitivity	-	gas-price-peak-mid-capex	gas-price-peak-low-capex

- Low and medium Iron-Air costs are the US\$15.00/kWh and US\$20.00/kWh 2030 target specifications with a US\$1.00/kWh Europe premium at an exchange rate of 1 € = 1.05 USD (as of January 25, 2025).

Multi-Day Storage (MDS) **deployed at up to 70 GW** across our modelled regions

Comparison of installed Iron-Air capacities (GW) in **total**:

Storyline \ Iron-Air cost	High Iron-Air cost (23.50 € ₂₀₂₄ /kWh)	Medium Iron-Air cost (20.00 € ₂₀₂₄ /kWh)	Low Iron-Air cost (15.25 € ₂₀₂₄ /kWh)
Climate year 2013	15.7	28.8	51.6
Climate year 2012	10.7	22.6	43.7
Climate year 1996	24.0	n.a.	n.a.
Climate year 2010	29.0	46.2	70.2
Mandated German gas phase out	n.a.	35.2	56.9
Delayed transmission expansion	n.a.	31.9	54.9
Gas price sensitivity	n.a.	28.4	51.5

Multi-Day Storage (MDS) **deployed at up to 31 GW** in Germany

Comparison of installed Iron-Air capacities (GW) in **Germany**:

Storyline \ Iron-Air cost	High Iron-Air cost (23.50 € ₂₀₂₄ /kWh)	Medium Iron-Air cost (20.00 € ₂₀₂₄ /kWh)	Low Iron-Air cost (15.25 € ₂₀₂₄ /kWh)
Climate year 2013	8.0	14.3	24.1
Climate year 2012	2.7	8.6	20.0
Climate year 1996	7.5	n.a.	n.a.
Climate year 2010	12.4	21.3	31.0
Mandated German gas phase out	n.a.	19.4	30.6
Delayed transmission expansion	n.a.	14.5	25.0
Gas price sensitivity	n.a.	14.2	24.1

Multi-Day Storage (MDS) deployed at up to 70 GW across our modelled regions with up to 31 GW in Germany

Figure 3: Installed Iron-Air capacities in Germany (left) and across modelled region (right) in 2035 for the 'baseline' scenario

Multi-Day Storage (MDS) deployed at up to 70 GW across our modelled regions with up to 31 GW in Germany

Figure 4: Installed Iron-Air capacities in Germany (left) and across modelled region (right) in 2035 for the 'nogasppe-low-capex' scenario

Multi-Day Storage (MDS) deployed at up to 70 GW across our modelled regions with up to 31 GW in Germany

Figure 5: Installed Iron-Air capacities in Germany (left) and across modelled region (right) in 2035 for the 'cy2010-low-capex' scenario

MDS reduces curtailment by up to 51% in Germany

Figure 6: Germany annual electricity curtailment by scenarios

MDS reduces curtailment by up to 51% in Germany

Storyline	Max. change to no-MDS scenario [%]
Climate year 2013	- 48 %
Climate year 2012	- 35 %
Climate year 1996	- 18 %
Climate year 2010	- 51 %
Mandated German gas phase out	- 48 %
Delayed transmission expansion	- 39 %
Gas price sensitivity	- 45 %

Especially **low-cost MDS** leads to a reduction between **35%** and **51%** for the low-capex scenarios.

Figure 7: Germany annual electricity curtailment 2013 climate year scenarios

MDS reduces curtailment by up to 51% in Germany

Figure 8: Germany annual electricity curtailment mandated gas phase out scenarios

- A mandated gas phase out introduces significant levels of curtailment into the system if no MDS is available **(+13.8%)**.
- With introduction of Iron-Air batteries, this effect can be largely reduced by **up to 48%** in the low-cost scenario showing the **potential of MDS to support a mandated gas phase out**.

MDS reduces curtailment by up to 51% in Germany

- The highest reduction of **up to 51%** in curtailment can be observed for the weather year 2010, characterized by the lowest annual wind availability.

Figure 9: Germany annual electricity curtailment 2010 climate year scenarios

MDS reduces curtailment by up to 51% in Germany, reducing the average price of electricity

Figure 10: Germany annual electricity curtailment 'no-mds' scenario

MDS reduces curtailment by up to 51% in Germany, reducing the average price of electricity

Figure 11: Germany annual electricity curtailment 'low-capex' scenario

MDS reduces curtailment by up to 51% in Germany, reducing the average price of electricity

CY2010 - No MDS

Figure 12: Germany annual electricity curtailment 'cy2010-no-mds' scenario

MDS reduces curtailment by up to 51% in Germany, reducing the average price of electricity

CY2010 - low-capex

- 12 TWh
- 6 TWh
- 3 TWh

Total annual curtailment:
81.436 TWh

Avg. Electricity Price:
92.12 EUR/MWh

Curtailment

- Onshore Wind
- Solar PV (rooftop)
- Solar PV (utility)
- Offshore Wind

Figure 13: Germany annual electricity curtailment 'cy2010-low-capex' scenario

MDS reduces the average price of electricity through flattening high price hours and lowering the price spread

Figure 14: Germany load weighted electricity price distribution by scenarios

MDS reduces the average price of electricity through flattening high price hours and lowering the price spread

Storyline	Max. change to no-MDS scenario [%]
Climate year 2013	- 5.3 %
Climate year 2012	- 5.9 %
Climate year 1996	- 3.0 %
Climate year 2010	- 6.9 %
Mandated German gas phase out	- 7.8 %
Delayed transmission expansion	- 5.9 %
Gas price sensitivity	- 5.3 %

- Up to **5.3%** reduction in **average** electricity price.
- Up to **19.5%** reduction in **extreme** electricity price.
- Up to **23.5%** increase in **median** electricity price (fewer frequencies of low electricity prices).

Figure 15: Germany load weighted electricity price distribution 2013 climate year scenarios

MDS reduces the average price of electricity through flattening high price hours and lowering the price spread

- Up to **6.9%** reduction in **average** electricity price.
- Up to **13.9%** reduction in **extreme** electricity price.
- Up to **500%** increase in **median** electricity price (fewer frequencies of low electricity prices).

MDS reduces the average price of electricity through flattening high price hours and lowering the price spread

- Up to **7.8%** reduction in **average** marginal price.
- Up to **62.7%** reduction in **extreme** marginal price.
- Up to **30.4%** increase in **median** marginal price (fewer frequencies of low electricity prices).
- Again, this shows the **potential of MDS to support a mandated gas phase out** by creating price stability.

Multi-Day Storage (MDS) supports achieving carbon emission targets

Germany annual power sector emission

Figure 18: Germany annual power sector emissions by scenarios

Components
 ■ CHP ■ Gas Turbine

■ Note: German gas power plants without carbon capture were exogenously excluded in 'nogasppde' scenarios.

Multi-Day Storage (MDS) supports achieving carbon emission targets

Storyline	Max. change to no-MDS scenario [%]
Climate year 2013	- 7.8 %
Climate year 2012	- 6.4 %
Climate year 1996	+ 1.2 %
Climate year 2010	- 3.7 %
Mandated German gas phase out	- 7.7 %
Delayed transmission expansion	- 7.3 %
Gas price sensitivity	- 8.2 %

■ Global emission limits are reached in all scenarios but power sector emission reduction for Germany of up to **8.2%** can be observed.

Figure 19: Germany annual power sector emissions 2013 climate year scenarios

Multi-Day Storage (MDS) supports achieving carbon emission targets

Components
■ CHP ■ Gas Turbine

- Delayed infrastructure projects increase German power sector emissions up to **25.9 MtCO2 (+6.15%)**.
- Inclusion of Iron-Air can **reduce this by 7.3%** back to similar levels as with baseline grid expansion showcasing the **potential of MDS to support the system in case of delayed transmission projects**.

Figure 20: Germany annual power sector emissions delayed transmission expansion scenarios

Multi-Day Storage (MDS) reduces power system cost in Germany

Multi-Day Storage (MDS) reduces power system cost in Germany

Germany electricity system cost

Figure 22: Germany electricity system cost 2013 climate year scenarios

Storyline	Max. change to no-MDS scenario [%]
Climate year 2013	- 2.21 %
Climate year 2012	- 1.08 %
Climate year 1996	- 1.63 %
Climate year 2010	- 1.96 %
Mandated German gas phase out	- 3.42 %
Delayed transmission expansion	- 1.89 %
Gas price sensitivity	- 2.20 %

Multi-Day Storage (MDS) reduces power system cost in Germany

Germany electricity system cost

- The largest reduction in power system cost (**3.42%**) can be observed when adding Iron-Air to a system with a mandated gas phase out in Germany.

Figure 23: Germany electricity system cost mandated gas phase out scenarios

Multi-Day Storage (MDS) reduces power system cost in Germany

Germany electricity system cost

Figure 24: Germany electricity system cost climate year sensitivity scenarios

Multi-Day Storage (MDS) reduces power system cost in Germany

- Climate year 2010 is significantly more demanding than the baseline Climate year 2013 leading to high power system cost of **60 billion EUR/a even in the low-capex** scenario.
- Nevertheless, a power system cost reduction of up to **1.96%** is observed with falling investment cost for multi-day storage.

Figure 25: Germany electricity system cost 2010 climate year scenarios

MDS is used to meet demand in multi-day lulls and reduces Li-Ion batteries and some CHP required in Germany

Figure 26: Germany energy balance February 14 - March 1 'baseline' scenario

MDS is used to meet demand in multi-day lulls and reduces Li-Ion batteries and some CHP required in Germany

Figure 27: Germany energy balance February 14 - March 1 'low-capex' scenario

MDS is used to meet demand in multi-day lulls and reduces Li-Ion batteries and some CHP required in Germany

nogaspde-low-capex

- | Components | | |
|-----------------------------------|----------------------------|-----------------------------|
| --- Electricity distribution grid | ■ Onshore Wind | ■ Electricity trade |
| ■ Solar PV (rooftop) | ■ Gas Turbine | ■ Li-Ion Battery Storage 8h |
| ■ Solar PV (utility) | ■ CHP CC | ■ Pumped Hydro Storage |
| ■ CHP | ■ Hydroelectricity | ■ BEV charger |
| ■ Offshore Wind | ■ Iron-Air Battery Storage | ■ Vehicle-to-Grid |

- MDS (+438 GWh) and additional imports (+1,934 GWh) can fill the gas power plant gaps meeting 6% and 22% of electricity demand in this 2 week period, respectively.

Figure 28: Germany energy balance February 14 - March 1 'nogaspde-low-capex' scenario

Iron air can also **reduces the dependence on critical raw materials** required for Li-Ion batteries by up to 90%

Figure 29: Relative share of German storage power capacity by scenarios

- Components
- Iron-Air Battery Storage
 - Li-Ion Battery Storage 8h
 - Adiabatic CAES
 - Pumped Hydro Storage
 - Vehicle-to-Grid

Iron air can also **reduces the dependence on critical raw materials** required for Li-Ion batteries by up to 90%

Relative change in installed **Li-Ion batteries in Germany compared to no MDS** counterfactuals:

Storyline \ Iron-Air cost	High Iron-Air cost (23.50 € ₂₀₂₄ /kWh)	Medium Iron-Air cost (20.00 € ₂₀₂₄ /kWh)	Low Iron-Air cost (15.25 € ₂₀₂₄ /kWh)
Climate year 2013	-35.5%	-56.1%	-80.4%
Climate year 2012	-13.5%	-34.0%	-67.2%
Climate year 1996	-32.3%	n.a.	n.a.
Climate year 2010	-39.8%	-67.8%	-90.6%
Mandated German gas phase out	n.a.	-57.2%	-78.7%
Delayed transmission expansion	n.a.	-39.7%	-62.7%
Gas price sensitivity	n.a.	-56.0%	-80.4%

Low-cost MDS has great potential to reduce curtailment, flatten electricity prices, and reduce resource dependence while helping to achieve emission targets

Iron-Air batteries ...

- have a large impact on a highly renewable German energy system by reducing curtailment.
- flatten electricity prices by lowering peak prices and reducing the frequency of extremely low prices.
- fill a gap during multi-day lulls, reducing the need for more Li-Ion batteries and critical raw materials.
- provide benefits that support a mandated gas power plant phase out and delays in transmission projects, especially during multi-day dark doldrums.
- offer a particularly strong case in extreme weather year scenarios, providing a hedge to increase the robustness of the system.
- provide benefits that improve significantly with falling investment cost for multi-day storage.

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